

THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY.

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about reforms in the field of culture and art, the role of music in the development of society, the influence of music on the education of young people, as well as the views, opinions and opinions of our ancestors on the art of music.

Keywords: music, culture, development, tradition, reform, art, education, music, society, sound, literature.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola madaniyat va san'at sohasidagi islohotlar, musiqa san'atining jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi o'rni, musiqaning yoshlar tarbiyasiga ta'siri, qolaversa ajdodlarimizning musiqa san'atiga bo'lgan qarashlari, fikr va mulohazalari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, madaniyat, taraqqiyot, an'ana, islohot, san'at, tarbiya, musiqa, jamiyat, tovush, adabiyot.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в области культуры и искусства, роли музыки в развитии общества, влиянии музыки на воспитание молодежи, а также взгляды, взгляды и мнения наших предков по музыкальному искусству.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, развитие, традиция, реформа, искусство, образование, музыка, общество, звук, литература.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these

requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

As we know, the art of music is considered a very ancient art form. It is known from ancient manuscripts that the ancient people were inextricably connected with the art of music in their social and domestic life. In particular, the sacred book of Zoroastrianism, which is considered an important source in the history of our ancestors, "Avesta", provides detailed information about it. In those times, people used musical sounds during work, hunting, farming, handicrafts, and even during war. For example, during the war, noisy musical instruments (drums, trumpets) were used to confuse the enemy in wartime strategies.

In particular, in the reign of our great grandfather Amir Temur, who left an indelible mark in the history of our nation, special attention was paid to the art of music and musicians, which indicates that our great grandfather occupied an important place in the development of the kingdom.

Amir Temur brought poets, architects, scientists and musicians to his palace from the territories he conquered, especially from the famous cities of that time, Baghdad, Damascus, as well as Iran, Khorasan, and paid respect to them. of course, the palace parties did not pass without musicians. Personally, Temur would have enjoyed listening to their songs. We can also see that he used it in the development of his country.[4]

Also, our Jadids have made detailed discussions about the role of music in bringing the people out of spiritual backwardness. In particular, one of the representatives of Jadidism, Abdulla Avloni, deeply understood that music plays an important role in human education, especially in the education of young people, like all modern intellectuals. adi. His article "Industrial Nafisa" published in the first issue of "Inqilab" magazine in 1922 proves our point in every way. Awlani popularly thought that "people in ancient times were the first human beings who created the beauty of human children on the face of the earth", "those who could not stop the influence and emotion in their hearts and did not lie down and remain silent without being satisfied with what they had achieved", "made nature and He explains that they began to look carefully at the animate and inanimate things that they created.

Leaves and trees and vegetables are happy with each other,
The nature of every page is life.

In other words, every green leaf of the trees is the leaf of the universe in the eyes of the alert (people). In this way, the writer emphasizes that the simple imitation of nature lies in the birth of the art of music. In the scientific literature of Avloni,

he is mostly correct in analyzing the times called “the era of imitation” and “the era of oral creativity of the people”. expresses the period as follows: “when they became conscious of the pleasant sounds of the birds that were drunk in the migration of smallpox in the spring season, they involuntarily tried to imitate the sounds of those birds and sing like birds”. the desire for beauty, music, creativity, and the ability to create a unique melody, and the music that gives birth to this inclination and its awakening, radiates that the bride of the seasons is spring. Defining the period: They are also songs “They started to sing. This period is called the literary period of industrial sophistication”, says the writer. He wrote the poem “Music” because he was devoted to music.

Your body is melodious, your words are holy

When Rukhbakhshadur chants, your eyes are closed

Avlani describes music in a beautiful image that breathes life into a dead body. The sound of music subjugates the human spirit and enraptures thousands of souls. Whoever hears the sound of music once in his life, it will forever be a ghost to him. Music is a human being. it gives joy to the soul and takes it captive. Thousands of souls have been touched and charmed by the source of music, “dead hearts”, that is, dead hearts also receive medicine from its influence and come back to life. Avlani believes that the soul of a person who understands and enjoys music is pure, does not change to evil, and does not get corrupted. At the same time, the poet emphasizes that music has the power to educate and purify the human spirit and spirituality, and “purification” of the ancient Greek philosophers. agrees with the concept.[5] In addition, it is known from historical works that our great-grandfathers, such as Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi, Alisher Nawai, wrote many works dedicated to music and were directly engaged in music. It is not wrong to say that his researches on the improvement of the oud instrument gave a great impetus to the development of our national instruments. In addition, Hazrat Navoi also used musical paints in his poetic and artistic thinking to embody the image of musical proportions, figurative similes, complete and holistic images, also widely used musical adjectives. For example, Dilorom in the epic “Sabbayi Sayyor” can’t be imagined without a dust song, or without a melody, in the seventh climate of this work, the alien from Khorezm without “Ilmu advoru science musical”.[6]

Even today, if we look at the development of developed countries, we can see that special attention is paid to the art of music. Especially in Japan, the USA, Germany, and Hungary, special attention is paid to music lessons. special attention is paid to the education of children of this age, because it is precisely in

this age that the desire and serious attitude towards academic subjects is brought up. In addition, music education is highly paid attention to in Hungary. In the third and fourth grades, students have the opportunity to get acquainted with music literature and learn some musical instrument.[7]

In conclusion, we can understand that the art of music can serve as an important factor in the development of society, and in addition, music can serve as an important tool in instilling moral values such as patriotism, charity, kindness, and friendship in the young generation. we will be helped by the national melodies of our people, which have been recited for many years, folk art and songs that are embedded in our national spirit. In fact, we would not be mistaken if we say that music serves as an important tool for the spiritual purification and spiritual growth of a person. Today's reforms in the field of art and culture are a clear proof of our above thoughts

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp.
2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.
3. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Solomonova T. History of Uzbek music. T. 1981.- P.20.
5. Kadirov. P. "Singing loudly in elementary school". - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1997.- P.16.
6. Boymirzayev H. "Methodology of learning music". - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1995.- P.12.
7. Sharipova G. "Music and its teaching methodology". - T. "Turon-Iqbal" publishing house, 2011.- P.46.

